

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN PROVIDING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF THE ATHLETE

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Abstract: *This article discusses what the development of an athlete's character should focus on in the course of his or her activities and the recommendations of scientific research on the formation of an athlete's psychological education and mental management skills. The article also contains the author's scientific proposals and practical recommendations on this issue.*

Keywords: *Hypothermia, basic psychological preparation, spasms, sense of rhythm.*

The development of an athlete's character takes place during his active activity and in connection with the athlete's physical activity. At a time when physical culture and sports are rapidly developing in our country, one of the important issues is to improve the activities of athletes and their training. The development of the spiritual and moral qualities of every young athlete, the assessment of their intellect and intelligence, the development of their abilities and human qualities, the emphasis on physical and mental preparation for their development as professionals, bring positive results.

These psychological traits and qualities can be given to our athletes by the coach and the team psychologist.

What should an athlete pay more attention to during physical education and sports activities? First of all, it's about self-awareness. to understand themselves as individuals, to understand their interests, aspirations, experiences. The experience of different emotions that come with self-knowledge shapes the attitude towards oneself, which in turn shapes the athlete's self-esteem. It has two sides - meaningful (knowledge) and emotional (attitude). Knowledge of oneself is intertwined with knowledge of others and ideals. As a result, the athlete is judged on what is better and worse than others and how it fits into the ideal. Thus, self-esteem is the result of comparative self-knowledge, not a description of the possibilities available. the athlete sets specific goal goals, i.e., has a certain level of challenge, which should be commensurate with his or her actual capabilities. If the level of aspiration is not sufficiently assessed, it can limit the athlete's initiative and activity in physical development; Excessive exercise can lead to frustration and loss of self-confidence.

Thus, in the process of physical culture, the impact occurs not only on the biological basis of the athlete, but also on his biosocial integrity. Therefore, a person's physical culture cannot be judged solely on the basis of the development of his physical abilities, without taking into account the level of development of his thoughts, feelings, values, orientations and interests, needs, beliefs.

Athlete's physical culture is determined by factors such as social. First of all, each athlete understands the essence and rules of training, methods of organization of physical activity, ways and means of physical development, the laws of the body in the process of physical activity, motor activity and its social, moral and spiritual aspects. It is legitimate to put the level of knowledge, depth, completeness and thoroughness of the knowledge, and has aesthetic significance.

Athletes need to consider the internal factors that can lead to injuries during competitions and pre-training. These include exercise in conditions of fatigue and overwork, as well as the presence of foci of chronic infection in the body, the tendency to vascular and muscle spasms, and other painful conditions.

To prevent hypothermia and overheating, it is important to take into account weather factors (temperature, humidity, wind), the degree of hardening of the listeners, and the suitability of clothing and footwear to these factors.

The potential damage to the body caused by different types of exercise needs to be carefully studied and analyzed to develop specific measures to prevent and eliminate the conditions that occur.

“Psychological training is aimed at developing the skills of calmness, self-control, the most favorable psychological state in cases of strong nervous tension (fatigue, strong competition, making mistakes, leadership, etc.). system of psychological and pedagogical measures ”. The system of psychological training includes the following:

- 1- basic psychological training
- 2- psychological preparation for exercises;
- 3- psychological preparation for competitions;
- 4- post-competition psychological preparation

On the basis of the following system, on the one hand, the psychological characteristics of the sport, on the other hand, the psychological aspects of the athlete are nurtured.

It consists of compiling a list of psychological functions, traits and qualities of a person that are necessary to achieve high results in sports. This list can be as follows:

- high activity of visual, auditory, vestibular and motor analysis
- concentration, accuracy of imagination, good memory, speed of thinking, depth and flexibility, rich imagination
- high level of physical abilities.
- Musical abilities: listening to music, sense of rhythm, ability to listen to and understand music: purposefulness, perseverance, patience, self-control, initiative.

Ability to manage psychological situations, to resist negative influences. Psychological education and the formation of mental management skills, concentration, mobilization of all forces, the formation of skills to resist negative influences require special skills, and these skills are taught to the team in the course of special theoretical and practical training. is shaped by the psychologist and to some extent the coach

These psychological traits and qualities can be given to our athletes by the coach and the team psychologist.

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